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Effects of Novel Substrates in electricity generation in a mediator-less microbial fuel cell

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ABSTRACT

The use of Microbial Fuel Cells to produce electricity is an area that has attracted attention recently owing to clean and renewable energy produced by the use of bacteria to catalyze the conversion of organic matter into electricity. The experiment was done in a mediator-less Microbial Fuel Cell with cassava mother liquid, human urine, human urine with faeces, swine waste and brewery waste as substrates using potassium ferricyanide as electron acceptor. The result of the experiment indicates that cassava mother liquid, human urine and swine waste generated a maximum potential difference of 1.32V each and also maximum current of 2.28A, 2.19A and 2.02A respectively. However, human urine with faeces and brewery waste was observed to be lower with values 1.13V and 1.15V respectively and corresponding lower currents of 1.45A and 1.40A respectively. It was observed that human urine is most stable with potential difference and current of 1.32V and 1.58A respectively. This may be attributable to the rich organic compounds such as carbohydrate, nitrogen, ammonium, potassium and phosphorous in urine which are good sources of fuel.

Keywords: Microbial fuel cell, Electricity generation, mediatorless.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, attention has shifted to renewable electricity generation sources owing to the pollution effects of fossil fuel. The reasons for the recent interest in using bacteria to generate electricity are a combination of the need for new sources of energy, discoveries about microbial physiology related to electron transport, and advancement of fuel cell technologies (Nwahia and Opara, 2014). The system can generate clean energy (Liu et al., 2004; Oh et al., 2004; Aelterman et al., 2006; Mokhtarian et al., 2012). Logan and Regan, 2006 stated that Microbial Fuel cells have certain advantages like high-energy conversion efficiency, mild reaction conditions and with fuel cell's emissions well below environmental regulations (Nwahia and Opara, 2014).

Energy is transformable and microbial fuel cell technology provides the required process to transform chemical energy stored in an organic matter to electricity. Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) are a biochemical-catalyzed system that produces electricity by oxidizing biodegradable organic matter in the presence of either fermentative bacterial or enzyme (Mokhtarian et al., 2012). Different kinds of substrate, simple organic and inorganic substrate or waste water as mixed combination of several materials can be used in MFCs as electron donors (Habermann and Pommer, 1991; Mokhtarian et al., 2012). According to Marthuriya and Sharma, 2009, the process of generating electricity using a microbial fuel cell involves the degradation of micro organisms in an anoxic chamber with the release of electrons that are captured and channelled externally to a final electron acceptor in an aerated compartment while at the same time protons released migrate through a permeable membrane (Kassongo and Togo, 2011). The potential difference between the proton and electron compartments produces the voltage that generates the electricity.

Rabaey et al., 2004; Rabaey and Verstraete, 2005 enumerated the parameters that affect the microbial fuel cells operation which include: (i) Metabolism of micro organisms (ii) transfer of produced electron (iii) proton exchange membrane performance (iv) materials resistance (v) cathode oxidation and (vi) substrate (Mokhtarian et al., 2012). The effect of the novel substrate in electricity generation will depend on the degradability of the substrates in the microbial fuel cell and also the ease of release of electrons. The essence of this work is to determine the effect of novel substrates in electricity generation in a mediator-less fuel cell. The findings from this research work will enhance the renewability and regeneration capacity of the microbial fuel cells.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Substrates

The substrates used are: (i) Human waste (urine) (ii) Human waste (faeces + urine) (iii) Animal waste (swine dung) (iv) Plant waste (cassava mother liquid) (v) Industrial waste (brewery waste). The cassava starch water known as cassava mother liquid was obtained from cassava grinding mill in Choba, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The liquid was kept for about 5 hours to settle, and then decanted. The pH for the cassava mother liquid is 7.0. Industrial waste (brewery waste) of pH 7.0 was collected from Pabod Breweries in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The other substrates: Human waste (faeces + urine), human waste (urine) and animal waste (swine dung) were collected at Choba, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Chemicals and analyses

Five custom two-chamber, H-shape MFCs were assembled for this study from pairs of flat-bottom, 1-litre cylindrical transparent plastic containers. Agar agar and salt (NaCl) were used in the experiment. Potassium Ferricyanide ($\text{KFe}(\text{CN})_6$) is used in cathode chamber as the proton acceptor. It is prepared by dissolving 8.23g in 250ml of distilled water. The pH meter (M12151 model) was employed to measure the pH values of the substrates.

Construction and connecting the IEM (Ion Exchange Membrane)

A $\frac{3}{4}$ inch PVC pipe was cut into 5 pieces of 0.06m each then PVC screw sockets (flanges) was fixed with epoxy at both ends of the pipe, thereby giving the pipe a new length of 0.1m. Each of the pipes was sterilized with ethanol to free the surface of the microorganism. And the open ends were sealed with masking tape to prevent microorganisms from acting on the internal surface after sterilization. Twenty grams of agar was measured and mixed with 3.75g of NaCl. Also 500ml of distilled water was added to the mixture and stirred. The prepared agar was autoclaved at 121°C for 20mins to gel, after which it was removed and poured into the sterilized pipe to solidify. After about 30mins of solidification, the IEM was ready for use.

Construction and operation of MFC

Two plastic bottles with lids for anode and cathode respectively were drilled from the side with about 1 inch diameter of hole. Iron exchange membrane was fixed with one end connected to the anode chamber and the other connected to the cathode chamber. Epoxy was used to seal and firmly fix the IEM to the chambers. Holes of about 0.01m were made on the lids for electrodes. Each set-up has one anode and cathode chamber. To operate the MFC, a salt bridge is connected between the two plastic bottles and *chikoku* (soil from mangrove swamp) is added to the anode chamber. A conductive solution of potassium ferricyanide is added to the cathode chamber. Thereafter, the anode and cathode are inserted into anode chamber and cathode chamber respectively. The different substrates were then poured into the 1.0L anode chamber of each five set-ups. The anode was covered and sealed to prevent oxygen from entering, because the anode chamber must be anaerobic. The cathode chamber (the oxidant) was filled with the catholyte (potassium ferricyanide) but was partially covered to allow enough oxygen which helps in oxidation.

Electrochemical measurements and calculations

The microbial fuel cell is intended to power an electric device constantly; a D.C. bulb of resistance 200Ω was connected across the cell throughout the duration of the experiment in a closed circuit. This contributed to high power generation for longer period, as those bacteria that were able to transfer electrons to the graphite electrode most efficiently gained a selective advantage because they could get more energy by losing electrons in that way (Opara, 2002). The microbial fuel cell voltage for the five-set ups was monitored daily using a digital multi-meter (ALDA, DT-830D) (Azunna et al., 2014). Voltage and current readings were done within few minutes of stabilization (Momoh and Neayor, 2010). Ohm's law ($I=V/R$) was applied to calculate the current and power density (P_d) calculated using: $P_d = (VI)/A$, where, V is the voltage, I is the current and A is the surface area (Kassongo and Togo, 2011). Power density is a function of power output (VI). Power output is controlled by a number of factors, including the efficiency of electron transfer from microorganisms to electrodes, electrode surface area, the resistance of the electrolyte and oxygen reaction kinetics in the cathode chamber (Zhen et al, 2005) Similarly, current density is calculated as current density $=I/A$ (Ampere/ m^2)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cultures started current generation after about 2 hours of inoculation (Day 0), but readings were taken daily from day 1.

Figure 1: Voltage and current generation during MFC Operation (a) Urine as substrate (b) Urine and Faeces as substrate

Figure 1a shows the voltage and current generation during MFC operation using human urine as substrate. There is an increase in voltage from 1.23V on day-1 to a maximum of 1.32V on day 28 to 30. But current generation reduced from 2.19A on day-1 to 1.58A on day-30. Figure 1b shows voltage generation with human urine and faeces as substrate. Voltage decrease was observed from maximum of 1.32V on day-3 to a minimum of 0.7V on day-30. Similarly, current generation also reduced from a maximum of 1.45A on day-3 to a minimum of 0.36A on day-30.

Figure 2: Voltage and Current generation of substrates during MFC Operation (a) Cassava mother liquid

Figure 2 shows voltage generation with cassava mother liquid substrate. It was observed that the voltage decreased from a maximum voltage of 1.32V on day-2 & 3 to a minimum of 0.95V on day-30.

Figure 3: Voltage and Current generation during MFC Operation using swine dung as substrate

Figure 3 shows voltage generation with swine dung as substrate. Increase in voltage was observed from 0.85V on day-1 to 1.18V on day-4, then to a maximum of 1.32V on day 22. Also current generation increased from 1.23A on day-1 to 2.1A on day-4 and then reduces to a minimum of 0.90A on day-30.

Figure 4: Voltage and Current generation of Brewery waste substrate during MFC Operation

Figure 4 shows voltage generation of Microbial Fuel Cell using Brewery waste as substrate. It was observed that the voltage decreased from the maximum voltage of 1.2V on day-3 to a minimum of 0.64V on day-30. Similarly, the current decreased from maximum value of 1.4A on day-3 to minimum value of 0.29A on day-30.

Figure 5: Power and current densities plot during MFC operation (a) using Urine as Substrate (b) Using Urine and faeces as substrate

Figure 5a shows the power and current densities plot of urine with respect to the graphite electrode size of 0.001408m^2 used in the experiment. Maximum power density of 1994.32W/m^2 was observed on day 3 while the minimum power density of 1246.45W/m^2 was observed on day 12. The current density has the maximum and minimum values of 1555.398A/m^2 and 1122.159A/m^2 respectively. Figure 5b shows the power and current densities plot of urine and faeces. Maximum power and current densities of 1359.375W/m^2 and 1029.83A/m^2 respectively were observed on day 3 with minimum power and current densities of 178.9773W/m^2 and 255.6818A/m^2 respectively observed on day 30.

Figure 6: Power and current densities plot during MFC operation using Cassava mother liquid as substrate

As can be observed in Figure 6, cassava mother liquid has a maximum power density of 2105.11W/m² on day 5 while day 30 recorded a minimum power density of 6.74716 W/m². The current density has the maximum value of 1505.68A/m² on day 1 and a minimum value of 7.10227A/m² on day 30.

Figure 7: Power and current densities plot during MFC operation (a) using Swine dung as Substrate

Figure 7: Power and current densities plot during MFC operation
(b) Using Brewery Waste as substrate

Figure 7a shows the power and current densities plot of swine dung during the MFC operation. Maximum power and current densities of 1759.94W/m^2 and 1491.477A/m^2 respectively were observed on day 4. The corresponding minimum values recorded on day 30 are 730.966W/m^2 and 639.2045A/m^2 respectively. Brewery waste in Figure 7b has a maximum power density of 1193.182W/m^2 on day 3 and a minimum value of 131.8182W/m^2 on day 30. The current density observed has maximum and minimum values of 994.3182A/m^2 and 205.965A/m^2 respectively.

However, it was observed that cassava mother liquid was the least stable with a total drop in current from a maximum of 2.28A on day-5 to 0.01A on day-30. Human urine substrate was the most stable at the end of the experiment with high potential difference and current of 1.32V and 1.58A respectively. It can be seen that cassava mother liquid has overall maximum power density of 2105.11W/m^2 but with also overall minimum power density of 6.74716W/m^2 . This may indicate that cassava mother liquid undergoes faster microbial degradation but of least power stability.

CONCLUSION

The use of cassava mother liquid, human urine with faeces, swine waste and brewery waste as substrate for Microbial Fuel cell has the potential to generate electricity during microbial degradation. Human urine substrate was the most stable at the end of the experiment with high potential difference and current of 1.32V and 1.58A respectively. The Microbial Fuel cell process has the potential of dual role of power generation and waste treatment.

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